

STRUCTURE OF SISAL FIBRE AND ITS USE IN DEVELOPMENT
OF SISAL CEMENT CORRUGATED ROOFING SHEET

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ABSTRACT

Sisal fibre is an important lignocellulosic fibre which grows all over the world in large quantities. This fibre is generally used for making high strength ropes and fancy articles. Use of sisal fibre for making fibre cement corrugated sheets was investigated to replace asbestos cement sheet. Because asbestos being carcinogenic is banned in many countries.

For making corrugated roofing sheets, surface of sisal fibre was modified by giving alkali treatment to the surface of fibre. After alkali treatment, the fibre was dried in open air. Alkali treatment to the surface of the fibre creates mechanical locking sites, removes the waxy materials, which helped in better bonding and in increasing the volume fraction of fibre content. It was necessary to optimise the treatment condition because the high concentration of alkali will reduce the tensile strength of the fibre. These fibres after alkali treatment were chopped and mixed with sand-cement slurry.

The sheet was cast in a corrugated mould, pressed, and was kept for 24 hours. The sheet was then removed from mould and kept for moist curing for 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ days.

The load bearing capacity was 2.0 Kg/cm per width, which is adequate for roofing purposes. The structure and purlins spacing can be designed suitably for placing the above sheets. The sheets also worked out to be cheaper than conventional asbestos sheet even after allowance for additional purlins. The sheet has superiority over asbestos sheet in respect of having no carcinogenic characteristics. This sheet does not pollute the atmosphere and is made up of local renewable materials. This sheet is cheaper as compared to asbestos cement sheet.

INTRODUCTION

Low cost housing has been described as the efficient use of local materials. Low cost building materials for mass

housing could be defined as the efficient development, production and appropriate use of indigenous materials. In most developing countries building materials used for building houses in rural and slum areas usually are earth (clay or soil) in its different forms (1) (abode, stabilised soil blocks etc.), stone, wood, concrete blocks, fired clay bricks, straw (for thatching), and corrugated sheets (roofing) and asbestos sheets.

Use of asbestos fibres in roofing elements is hazardous for health due to its carcinogenic nature. It is therefore necessary to investigate new type of materials which could replace asbestos. These raw materials could be low cost and available in large quantities (2). Sisal and other natural fibres fall in this category

The name sisal came from a harbour town in Yucatain Mexico. It means "cold water". Sisal fibre is obtained from the leaves of agave sisalana. It is estimated that the world production of sisal fibre is 0.6m tons per annum.

Sisal fibres are available in the 30-280 μ m diameter size, having a density of the order of 1.45 g/cc. Sisal fibre has 66-72% cellulose, 13-14% lignin with a moisture content 11%. Ultimate tensile strength of sisal fibre is of the order of 445 MPa with a modulus of 9.4 GPa and 3.5% elongation to break. This is mainly used for manufacture of ropes for use in marine industry and in agriculture. This fibre is also used in making twines, cords, mats, fishing nets, fancy articles such as purses, wall hangings, table mats etc. There are also reports to indicate the use of sisal fibre as reinforcement in polymer and cement matrixes and to use these natural fibre composites for potential applications in housing.

For better utilization of this fibre in developing cement sheet it was necessary to understand its structure, strength and surface morphology. It is also necessary to incorporate some high strength steel fibre or fabric in order to achieve the high flexural, or load bearing property of the sheet.

In this present paper structure of sisal fibre has been determined and is reported here. Sisal fibre have been incorporated in cement sheet which are stronger than any other natural fibre. Also on special steel fabric is incorporated in sisal cement sheet for increasing the strength. Sisal special fabric cement sheet is developed and load bearing capacity of 1m x 1m sheet was measured. Moisture absorption of sheet is determined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Preparation of sheets

The long sisal fibres were cut into approximately 15-20mm size and precoated with suitable coating and then mixed with cement and sand in suitable proportion. Water is added to make the mix workable. Corrugated sheets were cast in a mould incorporating a special fabric in the sheet. The sheet was demoulded after one day and left in air for curing under shade. Water is sprinkled once in a day to keep the sheet suitably moist. The sheet is ready for use after 28 days curing.

2. Testing of fibre and sheets

Microstructure of fibre was observed on stereo microscope by embedding the fibre in polyester block. Tensile tests of sisal fibre were carried out on INSTRON tensile testing machine by fixing the fibre in a card window of length 50mm. Sheets were tested for load bearing capacity, pitch of corrugation and for moisture absorption according to ISI methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sisal fibre like other natural fibres is a multicellular fibre having large number of cells as shown in the cross section (Fig.1a). Longitudinal section of sisal fibre is shown in Fig.1b. It is made of cellulose and lignin, etc. (5). Properties of this fibre determined are compared with the reported properties of asbestos fibres which are listed in Table 1.

Tensile fractograph of fibre is shown in Fig.2. Asbestos fibres is an inorganic fibre and has got nearly

Figure 1a. Cross section of sisal fibre x 120

Figure 1b. Longitudinal section of sisal fibre x 400

TABLE 1

Physical properties of asbestos fibre with sisal fibre

Property	Chrysotile*	Crocidolite*	Sisal
Colour	White to grey	Blue	White
Tensile strength psi (MPa)	3,00,000 (2068)	5,00,000(3448.2)	530-640
Modulus of elas- ticity psi(GPa)	23.2 x 10 ⁶ (160)	27.1 x 10 ⁶ (186)	9.4-22
Hardness, Mohs	2.5 - 4.0	4.0
Flexibility	Good	Fair	Good
Specific gravity	2.4 - 2.6	3.2 - 3.3	1.45

*Source : M. Xanthos and R.T. Woodhams Polymer encapsulation of colloid asbestos fibrils J.Appl.Polym.Sci. 1972 16 381.

Figure 2. Tensile fractograph of sisal fibre at a speed of 0.02 m/min speed of testing.

16-50 x 10⁴ psi tensile strength. During sheet making and using sisal fibre will come in contact of water. The effect of water absorption by the fibres depend on how rapidly they absorb the water, and the effect of this moisture on the fibre properties. Sheet made up of using sisal fibre after treatment is shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3. Sheet made up of using sisal fibre

The cracking of bamboo reinforced as the bamboo swell on taking up moisture, and the decrease in interfacial bond as it shrinks gave received considerable attention (5). It is necessary to have the good interfacial bonding between sisal fibre and cement sheet. Sisal fibre should not absorb moisture during curing and should not have much excess water.

Natural organic fibres of vegetable origin consist of cellulose molecules cross-linked with lignin, and are susceptible under normal conditions to fungal decay and termite

attack. Should this decay occur within the matrix, then the composite would finally consist of jute matrix with fibre-shaped voids. The reduction in strength and modulus below those of the matrix would also be relatively small because volume fraction of fibre will be very less.

On the other hand, the presence of the cement, could inhibit fungal and termite attack. At the same time, there would be the possibility of alkaline attack, as in case of glass fibres.

In order to make good bonding between fibre and cement surface of sisal fibre was treated for by alkali for 24 hrs and then the sheet was developed. Some other polymeric coatings to fibres are also proposed (4). Sheet was reinforced by a mesh for improving the strength particularly the load bearing capacity of the sheet. Properties of sisal-cement sheet are listed in Table-2. Sisal fibre does not degrade in marine water for longer times therefore, it will be very stable in cement sheet for longer times.

TABLE -2

Physical properties of the fibre cement sheet

1.	Size of corrugated sheet	1m x 1m
2.	Size of corrugations	46mm
3.	Pitch of corrugation	146mm
4.	a.Thickness of sheet	8-9mm
	b.Weight	17-18 Kg/m ²
5.	Loaded span	1m
6.	Breaking load	2.0 Kg per cm width
7.	Moisture absorption in 24 hours percent at 25 °C.	12% - 15%

CONCLUSIONS

Adequate load bearing strength of the fibre-fabric-cement sheet was obtained. The sisal fibre-fabric-cement sheet can be used to replace asbestos cement sheet although we may have to design the roofing trusses because the strength of this newly developed sheets are lower than the strength of the asbestos cement sheet.

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